

1 **Screening in the whole blood for major depressive disorder.**

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7 Our laboratory uses next-generation sequencing to identify and describe markers for use in diagnosis and
8 prevention of disease. Here, we measured total transcription in the blood, in healthy individuals and in
9 individuals with major depression, to discover genes that identify the individual with major depressive
10 disorder (MDD).

11 Citations

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